

FLIPPED CLASSROOMS: ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

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Abstract:

Flipped learning is a pedagogical approach in which the conventional notion of classroom-based learning is inverted, so that students are introduced to the learning material before class, with classroom time then being used to deepen understanding through discussion with peers and problem-solving activities facilitated by teachers. In traditional style teacher focuses on explaining the content using a lecture method. Student engagement in the traditional model may be limited to activities in which students work independently or in small groups on an application task designed by the teacher. Class discussions are typically centered on the teacher, who controls the flow of the conversation. In a Flipped classroom students are actively involved in knowledge acquisition and construction as they participate in and evaluate their learning. Efficient use of flipped classroom allows most students to do a year's work in much less time. Advanced students work on independent projects while slower learners get more personalized instruction. Some students might not get through the year's material, but demonstrated competence on the parts they did complete. My paper discusses merits and limitations in using flipped class technologies; and would the share the experience of the flipped class techniques followed in our class.

Key Words: Flipped Classrooms, Student Centered Learning, Knowledge Acquisition, Deep Understanding & Project Based Learnings.

Introduction:

In the present world of globalisation and in the 21st century senario technology has opened the doors of innovation in various fields and mainly in education. In recent times Flipped classrooms are playing vital role in teaching learning process. These classrooms throw a challenge to traditional classroom procedure. Flipped classrooms provide great scope for learners to enrich themselves with many skills which at large would help them be ready for the industry. The revolution of flipped classrooms help teachers to use their time in being more creative and proactive. They become more accessible to the slow learners and can motivate them in activities and tasks. The flipped classrooms assist in promoting a teacher's role from instructor to a guide, coach and a fecilitator. Teacher can motivate students to have deep knowledge on concepts and further help them to cultivate skills which would eventually lead to their empowerment.

The traditional methods of teaching and learning would encourage students to always depend on teacher and knowledge of concepts and theories would be limited. Students would find it difficult to complete the homework as they had to depend on teacher's lecture; which hardly allowed some students to grasp the lesson for the first time. In traditional classroom atmosphere students face problems of doing many things at a time like: listening to lecture, taking down notes and completing the worksheet. These classes gave less importance to creativity of students. But, in flipped classroom students learn the concepts, ideas before coming to class, depending on the suggestions given by teacher. It was teacher's responsibility to ask them to watch few videos, online ppts, podcasts, blogs and other web tools. At the same it was inevitable for teacher to do some research on all possible web tools; in order to be proactive.

In the present paper I would like to share some experiences of experimenting a flipped classroom technique in a English language class in our college. The first year undergraduate students were given 10 topics from Adous Huxley's prose "Benaras." Each topic was divided into 3 sub topics. Every student was given a topic, students were asked to collect information about the topic and each team had 3 members. They were suggested to use online sites, google down information or watch videos on you tube or take help from blogs. They had to write down few sentences and collect pictures about the topic and share the information with team mates. Later they took turns and explained about their research to the whole class. Finally they read the prose text and completed the task on reading comprehension. Whenever they found it difficult to comprehend I assisted them with hints and clues. I could interact and closely observe students working in teams. To my surprise each one was interested in completing all stages of work and was excited to be a part of whole process. They got a chance to learn deeply about each topic which made their interaction more interesting.

There are Many Advantages of Flipped Classrooms:

- ✓ Encourages Spirit of Research in Students: In flipped classroom students get to see what everybody else has seen and think what nobody else has thought. Teacher allots some concepts to students in class which they go home and find about those concepts by themselves .They make notes in their own style which paves way to original and unique understanding.

- ✓ Liberation in Homework: The flipped classroom technique gives ample scope for students to make their own choice of expressing views on the given concept. They get to watch, read and observe videos, information which gives them freedom to make notes. Previously students who took running notes which would always have a risk of missing points. But now students can pause, rewind and save the information to carry to class or for further use.
- ✓ Develops Collaborative Work Culture: Unlike traditional learning, in a flipped classroom students share the information they collect with their class mates. Eventually this technique encourages peer learning, project based learning etc. which encourages slow learners to learn and participate in sharing their views by putting aside their inhibitions. They are kept busy with the activities and tasks; moreover they get to seek help and personal attention from the teacher who was not approachable otherwise. The flipped classroom gives more freedom to teachers to zero on how much time to spend with each student. Struggling students, great performers, introverted kids, etc; can get the attention each of them need. In this case, a teacher gets chance to observe the students pace of learning and frames the instructions accordingly. The flipped class caters to the needs of irregular students who can catch up with the peer group faster and learn easily.
- ✓ Student Centered Classroom: The classrooms shifts focus from teacher needs to student needs as it stresses on student centred teaching approach. Teacher makes use of time in classroom by supporting students in grasping the concepts through practical application and giving hands on experience as they already have an idea of the concept.

The flipped classroom inspires teachers to offer a versatile and engaging way to share learning content, while shouldering more responsibility on students regarding their own career. At work place like-minded teachers can share resources, tips, to make successful flipped classrooms. While this model of education has not spread in each and every classroom yet, it seems like it's going there.

Limitations in Using Flipped Classrooms:

Flipping classrooms is inspiring teachers to change the way they've always done things, and it is motivating them to bring technology into their classrooms through the use of video and virtual classrooms.

- ✓ More Workload on Teachers: Teacher needs to spend more time in planning her lessons as each individual student has viability to watch various videos and tools. She must put in extra effort to make activities and tasks which would test the potential of all kinds of learners. Students show their mastery of content the way they like. "Are we doing things differently or doing different things?" As educators around the globe try to flip their class, it's an important thing to reflect on.
- ✓ Technical Issues: Access to internet is a must if students want do their projects and homework. Lack of technical knowledge or technology means no work or progress. There is another threat that students may spend more time in front of the screens and there is possibility of getting distracted.
- ✓ Initial Set Up Needs More Time: The teacher need to plan, organise and implement their lessons, task and activities in such a way that students find it interesting .In case of lack of technical knowledge or if students are unable to catch up with teacher's guidelines the whole purpose of it would be lost. The students need to have zeal to do new things. Only in few urban areas it would be possible to experiment. The standard and socio economic background of the student and teacher plays a vital role. Thus teacher needs to be more patient in working out things.
- ✓ Interest of Students: If students drop the idea of doing homework there is no room for flipped class. Teachers creativity primarily needs to focus on motivating students to do their homework.
- ✓ Not Every Ones Cup of Tea: The flipped classroom method would be more apt for self disciplined and self motivated students. Students should have good knowledge in coping with technical problems too, on the other hand in case of failure to complete the homework; it would demotivate the students further. It consumes more time for students to realise as to how they accustom with the new approach.
- ✓ Highly Expensive and Risky: In case of implementing flipped classrooms one needs to be financially ready to bear the cost of installing devices, projects, new curriculum and training the teachers in skills needed. The managements need to plan and decide on issues like at what level of teaching and which subjects and curriculum can be suitable for flipped class.
- ✓ Change May be a Bitter Pill: Teachers who though are aware of the drawbacks of traditional methods still don't mind carrying it but this change requires lot of efficiency, patience, willings to accept the change and self motivation. The teachers themselves need a lot of training in order to equip themselves with new trends in teaching and embrace innovative techniques. The more challenging role a teacher needs to play is with same amount of exuberance teacher requires to motivate students. Further there is still a doubt if one would be sure of accomplishing the targeted goals.

Conclusions:

The combination of flipped classroom with the just in time teaching approach may be a useful union to assist students to clear confusing material and develop deep learning strategies. It also helps in independent learning. There is no doubt that in present generation students are learning to work on projects, experiments,

activities to understand the concepts in various fields. The new approach may have some limitations but one must try to gain from the benefits of flipped classroom method in one way or the other. Whenever the teacher can implement this new approach it must be followed as this method needs more time to become user friendly. The other traits a student enriches shouldn't be left unseen; it promotes multi tasking, interpersonal skills, decision making skills and problem solving skills, on whole these skills would make the students equip for empowerment.

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